

Original Article

Molecular rejection signals in chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection: Histological associations and potential clinical implications

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ABSTRACT

Chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection (caTCMR) remains debated, and molecular diagnostics might aid risk-stratification. This retrospective two-center observational study analyzed 26 kidney allograft biopsies with caTCMR, comparing them to 40 borderline T cell-mediated rejection (bTCMR)/acute T cell-mediated rejection (aTCMR) cases (without caTCMR) and 308 subthreshold/negative controls after excluding microvascular inflammation at/above threshold and overlapping pathologies. All biopsies received transcriptomic evaluation through microarray-based gene expression profiling. caTCMR cases with aTCMR ($n = 8$) showed higher molecular T cell-mediated rejection (TCMR) activity (median probability of molecular TCMR [TCMR_{prob}] 0.54 [0.30-0.83]) than “pure” caTCMR ($n = 11$; TCMR_{prob} 0.03 [0.01-0.28], $P = .012$) or caTCMR with bTCMR ($n = 7$; TCMR_{prob}

Abbreviations: AKI, acute kidney injury; AMR, antibody-mediated rejection; aTCMR, acute T cell-mediated rejection; BKN, BK-virus nephropathy; bTCMR, borderline T cell-mediated rejection; caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection; ci, interstitial fibrosis; ct, tubular atrophy; cv, vascular fibrous intimal thickening; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; g, glomerulonephritis; GN, glomerulonephritis; HR, hazard ratio; i, interstitial inflammation; IFTA, interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; i-IFTA, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; IRRAT, injury-related repair-associated transcripts; MMDx, Molecular Microscope Diagnostic System; MVI, microvascular inflammation; prob, probability of (eg, TCMR_{prob}, probability of molecular acute TCMR); ptc, peritubular capillaritis; t, tubulitis; TCMR, T cell-mediated rejection; ti, total inflammation; t-IFTA, tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; v, arteritis.

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0.01 [0.01–0.77], $P = .036$). $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ was low in subthreshold/negative controls but elevated in aTCMR, BK-virus nephropathy and pyelonephritis cases (side cohort). Molecular sign-outs classified 4 of 11 (36%) “pure” caTCMR cases as molecular TCMR. Within the TCMR continuum (26 caTCMR plus 40 bTCMR/aTCMR), interstitial inflammation, tubulitis, and total inflammation-lesions were associated in univariable analyses with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$, while interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy/tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy correlated with molecular chronicity. Seven of 26 (27%) caTCMR and 7 of 40 (18%) bTCMR/aTCMR cases showed mixed molecular rejection activity above thresholds. In conclusion, significant molecular TCMR activity was present in a subset of caTCMR cases and was associated with higher inflammation/tubulitis/total inflammation scores and, at times, molecular antibody-mediated rejection signals, even with microvascular inflammation < 2 . To confirm these preliminary observations, future studies and external validation are needed.

1. Introduction

Chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection (caTCMR) is controversial and reported in 1% to 10% of kidney allograft biopsies, depending on the interpretation of Banff rules in clinical practice.^{1–3} Since introducing diagnostic criteria with the Banff 2017 update, diagnosis requires a meticulous evaluation, ensuring that confounders for inflammatory processes in scarred tissue (interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy [i-IFTA]) are excluded.⁴ Even if caTCMR is accurately diagnosed, treatment approaches vary across transplant centers. A 2019 Banff survey revealed that only 36% actively treat caTCMR.⁵ Moreover, there is no consensus on the optimal treatment, with strategies ranging from intensification of maintenance immunosuppression to pulsed steroids combined with T cell depletion.⁵

The histopathological Banff classification of disease-defining lesions may be subject to interobserver variability and relies on semiquantitative scoring. In contrast, molecular diagnostics, such as biopsy-based transcriptomics, offer the potential for a more nuanced disease phenotyping while following continuous classifiers.⁶ Large training data sets established cutoffs and correlations between molecular classifiers and histologic lesions in T cell-mediated rejection (TCMR), antibody-mediated rejection (AMR), and other markers of graft injury or rejection.⁶ Yet, detailed investigations into the clinical application of molecular diagnostics in histologic caTCMR cases remain limited, and potentially disease-specific transcripts remain to be further explored and validated.^{7,8}

Observational studies suggested that caTCMR independently impacts outcomes, with treatment nonresponse significantly affecting allograft survival.^{9,10} However, identifying individuals who benefit from antirejection treatment remains challenging. In our two-center cohort (Prague and Zurich), we analyzed kidney allograft biopsies using histologic assessment and molecular evaluation via the Molecular Microscope Diagnostic System (MMDx) to observe the molecular profile of caTCMR within the TCMR continuum and inflammation spectrum—acknowledging that caTCMR was not part of the training

set of MMDx. Our aim was to describe the molecular signatures that MMDx reveals in cases with histologic caTCMR-specific lesions, and to examine how the individual histologic lesions defining caTCMR relate to their molecular counterparts.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study cohort

Primary analyses comprised 26 Banff-defined caTCMR cases (all caTCMR grade I), deducted from 755 prospectively collected kidney allograft biopsies from 2 centers (452 from Zurich, 303 from Prague) between 2018–2025. According to Banff 2019/2022, caTCMR grade I was defined by total inflammation (ti) ≥ 2 and i-IFTA ≥ 2 with at least tubulitis (t) 2 or tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy (t-IFTA)2 (grade IA), or t3/t-IFTA3 (grade IB). As a deviation from the current Banff classification, we defined cases fulfilling caTCMR grade I criteria with vascular involvement ($v \geq 1$) as caTCMR stage II.^{5,11,12} Furthermore, cases with interstitial inflammation (i) < 2 and t < 2 but $v \geq 1$ were classified as borderline TCMR (bTCMR) with v-lesions, rather than acute TCMR (aTCMR) grade II, following recent studies.¹³ caTCMR grade II, defined by vascular intimal fibrosis (vascular fibrous intimal thickening [cv]-lesion), was not considered, as preliminary analyses showed no association between higher cv and molecular TCMR activity (Supplementary Fig. S1). The 26 caTCMR cases and the rest of the study cohort were selected based on strict exclusion criteria applied to the total two-center cohort ($n = 755$). Biopsies exhibiting microvascular inflammation (MVI) at/above the diagnostic threshold ($MVI \geq 2$), and/or fulfilling active/chronic-active AMR criteria were excluded. Biopsies with overlapping pathologies that confound the assessment of TCMR- or AMR-related lesions, such as BK-virus nephropathy (BKN), glomerulonephritis (GN), or pyelonephritis, were also removed from the main analyses, with some kept in a side cohort. Furthermore, we excluded biopsies with C4d positivity ($C4d > 1$), isolated arteritis (v-lesions), or missing values within the relevant Banff lesions. C4d staining was assessed via

Figure 1. Deduction of the study cohort. Kidney allograft biopsies conducted between 2018 and 2025 are considered. Histological details are described in the Materials and Methods section and in [Supplementary Table 1](#). AMR, antibody-mediated rejection; aTCMR, acute T cell-mediated rejection; bTCMR, borderline T cell-mediated rejection; caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection; g, glomerulitis; i, interstitial inflammation; i-IFTA, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; MVI, microvascular inflammation; ptc, peritubular capillaritis; t, tubulitis; TCMR, T cell-mediated rejection; ti, total inflammation; t-IFTA, tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; v, arteritis.

immunofluorescence (eg, positive, if C4d >1); however, in the context of ABO-incompatible kidney transplantation, without features of MVI, C4d positivity was interpreted as accommodation. BKN was diagnosed by positive simian virus 40 immunohistochemical staining with compatible histology. Ultimately, 374 biopsies formed the study cohort. An additional 33 biopsies fulfilled histologic caTCMR grade I criteria (t/t-IFTA ≥ 2 , ti ≥ 2 , and i-IFTA ≥ 2) but demonstrated superimposed features such as AMR/MVI or overlapping pathologies; these were analyzed separately. Biopsy samples from the main study cohort were categorized into 4 main histologic subgroups: (A) Banff-defined caTCMR (n = 26); (B) positive controls (bTCMR or aTCMR without fulfilled caTCMR criteria, n = 40); (C) subthreshold controls (n = 177); and (D) negative controls (biopsies without any active inflammation, n = 131). A + B represented the TCMR continuum, while A + B + C was defined as “Inflammation spectrum.” The deduction is visualized in [Figure 1](#) with histologic subgroups explained in [Supplementary Table 1](#).

2.2. Biopsy evaluation

Biopsy evaluation included histopathological lesion scoring, applying the updated Banff 2022 classification, and molecular

analysis through MMDx using microarray-based gene expression profiling.¹¹ Allograft biopsies were evaluated by 7 different and specifically trained nephropathologists at both centers (5 from Prague, 2 from Zurich). All 755 biopsies from our combined database were deemed “adequate” according to Banff criteria. For MMDx, a 2 to 3 mm portion of 1 of the biopsy cores was cut, placed into RNAlater solution, and stored until shipped for analysis. Protocol biopsies were performed at 3 and 12 months. The Zurich center started preserving biopsy samples in 2018. From 2021 onward, both newly obtained and previously stored biopsies were sent to the MMDx provider in Kashi Clinical Laboratories (Portland, OR, USA). Since 2022, Prague has performed in-house MMDx using the same algorithm and normalization strategy, with the same reference set of 1208 biopsies.

2.3. Objectives and molecular definitions

The objectives of this study were to assess the molecular signatures within caTCMR cases (n = 26) and to investigate the association between histologic Banff lesions and TCMR classifier activity (TCMR_{prob}) in a broader range of the TCMR continuum (n = 66), the inflammation spectrum (n = 243) and the whole study cohort including a negative control group (n = 374).

Table 1
Baseline and biopsy characteristics.

Variables	Study cohort (n = 374)	A: Banff-defined caTCMR (n = 26)	B: positive control (n = 40)	C: subthreshold control (n = 177)	D: negative control (n = 31)
Age at bx (y)	51 (41, 62)	53 (41, 61)	52 (36, 66)	51 (42, 62)	51 (42, 61)
Female sex, n (%)	144 (39)	10 (38)	11 (28)	74 (42)	49 (37)
Living donation, n (%)	84 (22)	7 (27)	7 (18)	42 (24)	28 (21)
Bx after TPL (mo)	6 (2, 53)	13 (4, 53)	3 (0, 5)	16 (3, 82)	3 (0, 29)
Indication bx, n (%) ^a	294 (79)	20 (77)	26 (65)	145 (82)	103 (79)
Indication eGFR	184 (49)	16 (62)	22 (55)	77 (44)	69 (53)
Indication proteinuria	51 (14)	3 (12)	2 (5)	28 (16)	18 (14)
Indication dnDSA	96 (26)	4 (15)	4 (10)	61 (34)	27 (21)
Indication other ^b	14 (4)	1 (4)	1 (3)	7 (4)	5 (4)
Protocol bx, n (%)	80 (21)	6 (23)	14 (35)	32 (18)	28 (21)
SCr at bx ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) ^c	159 (119, 224)	159 (123, 227)	186 (136, 246)	155 (120, 215)	161 (113, 248)
eGFR at bx ($\text{mL}/\text{min}/1.73 \text{ m}^2$) ^c	41 (28, 58)	41 (24, 55)	34 (28, 55)	42 (28, 57)	42 (24, 60)
UPCR at bx (mg/g) ^d	120 (60, 340)	340 (108, 540)	53 (19, 190)	120 (70, 330)	130 (58, 320)
Any DSA at bx, n (%)	185 (49)	9 (35)	22 (55)	89 (50)	65 (50)
Follow-up after bx (mo)	19 (10, 29)	19 (10, 29)	29 (10, 27)	24 (10, 33)	17 (10, 26)

Categorical variables are demonstrated as numbers and percentages of the total. Continuous variables are shown as median (interquartile range; Q1, Q3). Baseline and biopsy characteristics of more detailed subgroups are available in [Supplementary Table 2](#). eGFR is calculated by the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration equation of 2021.¹⁶

Bx, biopsy; caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection; dnDSA, de novo donor-specific antibody; DSA, donor-specific antibody; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; SCr, serum creatinine; TPL, transplantation; UPCR, urinary protein-creatinine ratio.

^a More than 1 biopsy indication possible (eg, proteinuria and dnDSA).

^b For eg, rise in antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody vasculitis titers.

^c Data on n = 372.

^d Data on n = 235.

Table 2
Histologic characteristics of the subgroups.

Variables	Study cohort (n = 374)	A: Banff-defined caTCMR (n = 26)			B: positive control (n = 40)			C: subthreshold control (n = 177)			D: negative control (n = 131)
		caTCMR (pure) (n = 11)	caTCMR + bTCMR (n = 7)	caTCMR + aTCMR (n = 8)	bTCMR (n = 24)	bTCMR + v-lesion (n = 8)	aTCMR (n = 8)	Subthreshold caTCMR (n = 115)	i-IFTA ≥2 alone (n = 14)	ISO-T (n = 48)	
		Banff active lesions, mean (SD)									
i-lesion	0.22 ± 0.58	0.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	2.38 ± 0.48	1.00 ± 0.00	1.12 ± 0.35	2.50 ± 0.53	0.03 ± 0.16	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
t-lesion	0.73 ± 0.85	1.55 ± 0.66	2.43 ± 0.49	2.63 ± 0.48	1.46 ± 0.72	1.62 ± 0.52	2.62 ± 0.52	0.82 ± 0.64	0.00 ± 0.00	1.15 ± 0.36	0.00 ± 0.00
v-lesion	0.06 ± 0.28	0.18 ± 0.57	0.29 ± 0.45	0.88 ± 0.78	0.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	0.50 ± 0.76	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
g-lesion	0.28 ± 0.45	0.27 ± 0.45	0.00 ± 0.00	0.38 ± 0.48	0.12 ± 0.34	0.25 ± 0.46	0.00 ± 0.00	0.32 ± 0.47	0.36 ± 0.50	0.23 ± 0.42	0.31 ± 0.46
ptc-lesion	0.05 ± 0.22	0.09 ± 0.29	0.14 ± 0.35	0.50 ± 0.50	0.08 ± 0.28	0.00 ± 0.00	0.12 ± 0.35	0.05 ± 0.22	0.00 ± 0.00	0.02 ± 0.14	0.03 ± 0.17
g + ptc (MVI) score	0.33 ± 0.47	0.36 ± 0.48	0.14 ± 0.35	0.88 ± 0.33	0.21 ± 0.41	0.25 ± 0.46	0.13 ± 0.35	0.37 ± 0.48	0.36 ± 0.50	0.25 ± 0.43	0.34 ± 0.47
Banff active and chronic lesions, mean (SD)											
ti-lesion	0.47 ± 0.78	2.27 ± 0.45	2.14 ± 0.35	2.50 ± 0.50	0.88 ± 0.45	1.00 ± 0.53	1.88 ± 1.25	0.62 ± 0.64	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
i-IFTA-lesion	0.82 ± 1.08	2.45 ± 0.50	2.43 ± 0.49	2.88 ± 0.33	0.54 ± 0.78	1.25 ± 1.28	0.25 ± 0.46	1.60 ± 0.89	2.29 ± 0.47	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
t-IFTA-lesion ^a	0.48 ± 0.75	2.44 ± 0.50	2.17 ± 0.69	2.00 ± 0.71	0.32 ± 0.65	0.67 ± 1.03	0.33 ± 0.82	0.76 ± 0.63	0.00 ± 0.00	0.33 ± 0.64	0.08 ± 0.30
Banff chronic lesions, mean (SD)											
ci-lesion	1.01 ± 0.70	2.27 ± 0.45	1.86 ± 0.64	1.13 ± 0.60	1.00 ± 0.29	1.00 ± 0.53	0.75 ± 0.46	1.20 ± 0.75	1.07 ± 0.92	0.79 ± 0.54	0.78 ± 0.59
ct-lesion	1.12 ± 0.60	2.27 ± 0.45	1.86 ± 0.64	1.25 ± 0.43	1.00 ± 0.29	1.12 ± 0.35	0.50 ± 0.53	1.32 ± 0.61	1.36 ± 0.63	0.96 ± 0.46	0.90 ± 0.49
cv-lesion	1.49 ± 0.93	1.91 ± 1.16	1.71 ± 0.45	1.13 ± 0.93	1.54 ± 0.83	1.50 ± 0.93	0.88 ± 0.83	1.56 ± 0.92	1.36 ± 0.84	1.42 ± 1.03	1.48 ± 0.91
cg-lesion ^b	0.29 ± 0.57	0.00 ± 0.00	0.43 ± 0.73	0.38 ± 0.48	0.08 ± 0.28	0.38 ± 1.06	0.00 ± 0.00	0.38 ± 0.64	0.50 ± 0.65	0.31 ± 0.62	0.25 ± 0.50
Chronicity scores/indices, n (%)											
ci + ct ≤2 (mild IFTA)	307 (82)	0 (0)	2 (29)	6 (75)	23 (96)	7 (88)	8 (100)	85 (74)	10 (71)	46 (96)	120 (92)
ci + ct ≥5 (Severe IFTA)	14 (4)	3 (27)	1 (14)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	8 (7)	1 (7)	1 (2)	0 (0)
ci + ct + cv + 2 × cg ≥4 ^b	222 (59)	11 (100)	7 (100)	4 (50)	15 (62)	4 (50)	1 (12)	83 (72)	7 (50)	25 (52)	65 (50)
ah + aah ≥2	223 (60)	7 (64)	5 (71)	3 (38)	11 (46)	3 (38)	2 (25)	79 (69)	8 (57)	29 (60)	76 (58)
Glomerulosclerosis >20% ^c	78 (21)	5 (45)	2 (29)	1 (13)	2 (8)	1 (13)	0 (0)	39 (34)	6 (43)	6 (13)	16 (12)

Categorical variables are demonstrated as numbers and percentages of the total. Continuous variables are shown as mean (SD). Glomerulosclerosis is defined as the percentage of globally sclerotic glomeruli among the total number of glomeruli per biopsy.

aah, hyaline arteriolar thickening; ah, arteriolar hyalinosis; aTCMR, acute T cell-mediated rejection; bTCMR, borderline T cell-mediated rejection; caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection; cg, glomerular basement membrane double contours; ci, interstitial fibrosis; ct, tubular atrophy; cv, vascular fibrous intimal thickening; g, glomerulitis; i, interstitial inflammation; IFTA, interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; i-IFTA, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; ISO-T, isolated tubulitis; MVI, microvascular inflammation; ptc, peritubular capillaritis; SD, standard deviation; t, tubulitis; ti, total inflammation; t-IFTA, tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; v, arteritis.

^a Data on n = 328.

^b Data on n = 372.

^c Data on n = 369.

A threshold of 0.1 was considered the upper limit of normal, and a threshold of 0.2 was considered molecular TCMR, in line with the established recommendations.^{14,15} Additionally, other rejection-related (AMR_{prob}) or lesion-specific molecular classifiers were analyzed, along with key injury scores. These included acute kidney injury (AKI) scores, reflecting injury-related repair-associated transcripts (IRRAT), and atrophy-fibrosis (interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy [IFTA]) scores. Archetype scores (R scores) and molecular sign-outs generated by the MMDx report were reported additionally. R scores are defined as: R1 = no rejection or injury; R2 = TCMR; R3 = mixed rejection; R4 = early-stage AMR; R5 = fully-developed AMR; R6 = late-stage AMR; all AMR (= R7; R4

+ R5 + R6) and all TCMR (= R8; R2 + R3). Death-censored allograft failure was assessed over a maximum of 36 months using a composite renal endpoint defined as persistent decline in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) >30% (at least 4 weeks of follow-up), a persistent eGFR below 15 mL/min/1.73 m² (also >4 weeks follow-up), or dialysis initiation. Allograft loss was defined as persistent eGFR below 15 mL/min/1.73 m² or the initiation of dialysis. Repeated biopsies (n = 41) and 6 biopsies with primary nonfunction were excluded from outcome observations. Fifteen patients died during follow-up before experiencing the outcome of interest, including 14 from the subthreshold or negative control group and 1 with bTCMR. The last day of follow-up was the 19th of March 2025.

Figure 2. Molecular acute T cell-mediated rejection (TCMR) classifier activity in histologic subgroups. (A) probability of molecular acute TCMR (TCMR_{prob}) in all histologic subgroups and subcategories presented as violin plots with median (interquartile range), as well as individual biopsy cases (dots). Dotted lines implicate the upper limit of normal (TCMR_{prob} 0.1) and the threshold for molecular acute TCMR (TCMR_{prob} 0.2). For P values: *P ≤ .05; **P ≤ .01. (B) Number of cases with TCMR_{prob} >0.2, TCMR_{prob} 0.1 to 0.2, and TCMR_{prob} <0.2 demonstrated as ring diagrams for each subgroup and subcategories. Below each ring diagram, the percentage (%) of cases above threshold (TCMR_{prob} >0.2) within the subcategory is indicated. aTCMR, acute T cell-mediated rejection; bTCMR, borderline T cell-mediated rejection; caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection; i-IFTA, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; v, arteritis.

Table 3
Molecular (MMDx) characteristics of the subgroups.

Variables	Study cohort (n = 374)	A: Banff-defined caTCMR (n = 26)			B: positive control (n = 40)			C: subthreshold control (n = 177)			D: negative control (n = 131)
		caTCMR (pure) (n = 11)	caTCMR + bTCMR (n = 7)	caTCMR + aTCMR (n = 8)	bTCMR (n = 24)	bTCMR + v-lesion (n = 8)	aTCMR (n = 8)	Subthreshold caTCMR (n = 115)	i-IFTA ≥2 alone (n = 14)	ISO-T (n = 48)	
Molecular rejection scores, median (IQR)											
Rejection _{prob}	0.05 (0.02, 0.20)	0.27 (0.08, 0.44)	0.06 (0.04, 0.52)	0.73 (0.43, 0.92)	0.22 (0.10, 0.43)	0.35 (0.26, 0.45)	0.71 (0.43, 0.83)	0.04 (0.02, 0.14)	0.03 (0.02, 0.15)	0.04 (0.03, 0.11)	0.03 (0.02, 0.08)
TCMR _{prob}	0.01 (0.00, 0.02)	0.03 (0.01, 0.26)	0.01 (0.01, 0.40)	0.54 (0.36, 0.80)	0.03 (0.01, 0.06)	0.03 (0.03, 0.22)	0.78 (0.62, 0.86)	0.01 (0.00, 0.02)	0.01 (0.01, 0.01)	0.01 (0.01, 0.02)	0.01 (0.00, 0.01)
AMR _{prob}	0.05 (0.04, 0.11)	0.09 (0.06, 0.17)	0.09 (0.03, 0.26)	0.13 (0.06, 0.26)	0.14 (0.05, 0.20)	0.14 (0.06, 0.22)	0.29 (0.15, 0.32)	0.05 (0.04, 0.08)	0.04 (0.03, 0.07)	0.05 (0.04, 0.08)	0.05 (0.03, 0.09)
AMR _{prob} >0.2, n (%)	48 (13)	2 (18)	2 (29)	3 (38)	6 (25)	3 (38)	5 (63)	6 (5)	2 (14)	4 (8)	15 (11)
g0 ptc0, n (% of AMR _{prob} >0.2)	27 (56)	2 (100)	1 (50)	0 (0)	3 (50)	3 (100)	5 (100)	3 (50)	1 (50)	1 (25)	8 (53)
g1 ptc0, n (% of AMR _{prob} >0.2)	15 (31)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (33)	2 (33)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (50)	1 (50)	2 (50)	6 (40)
g0 ptc1, n (% of AMR _{prob} >0.2)	6 (13)	0 (0)	1 (50)	2 (67)	1 (17)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (25)	1 (7)
Molecular injury scores, n (%)											
AKI (IRRAW) score											
Minimal/mild	270 (72)	5 (45)	5 (71)	1 (13)	17 (71)	4 (50)	2 (25)	88 (77)	11 (79)	40 (83)	97 (74)
Moderate/extensive	104 (28)	6 (55)	2 (29)	7 (88)	7 (29)	4 (50)	6 (75)	27 (23)	3 (21)	8 (17)	34 (26)
IFTA score											
Minimal/mild	272 (73)	2 (18)	5 (71)	5 (63)	19 (79)	5 (53)	7 (88)	73 (63)	10 (72)	41 (86)	105 (80)
Moderate/extensive	102 (27)	9 (82)	2 (29)	3 (38)	5 (21)	3 (38)	1 (13)	42 (37)	4 (28)	7 (14)	26 (20)
Predominant archetype, n (%)											
R1–NRI	312 (83)	6 (55)	5 (71)	2 (25)	15 (63)	3 (38)	1 (13)	104 (90)	13 (93)	46 (96)	117 (89)
R2–TCMR	27 (7)	4 (36)	1 (14)	4 (50)	3 (12)	2 (25)	7 (88)	6 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
R3–mixed rejection	5 (1)	0 (0)	1 (14)	2 (25)	1 (4)	1 (13)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
R4–EABMR	25 (7)	1 (9)	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (21)	2 (25)	0 (0)	3 (3)	0 (0)	2 (4)	12 (9)
R5–FABMR	2 (1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1)
R6–LABMR	3 (1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1)	1 (7)	0 (0)	1 (1)
Molecular sign-outs, n (%)											
Mixed molecular AMR/TCMR	13 (3)	0 (0)	2 (29)	2 (25)	2 (8)	1 (13)	4 (50)	1 (1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1)
Molecular AMR	30 (8)	1 (9)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (17)	2 (25)	0 (0)	4 (3)	2 (14)	3 (6)	14 (11)
Molecular possible AMR	23 (6)	0 (0)	1 (14)	0 (0)	4 (17)	0 (0)	0 (0)	10 (9)	0 (0)	2 (4)	6 (5)
Molecular TCMR	21 (6)	3 (27)	0 (0)	5 (63)	3 (12)	2 (25)	3 (38)	4 (3)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1)
Molecular possible TCMR	8 (2)	1 (9)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (3)	0 (0)	1 (2)	1 (1)
No molecular rejection	279 (75)	6 (55)	4 (57)	1 (13)	10 (42)	3 (38)	1 (13)	92 (80)	12 (86)	42 (88)	108 (82)

Categorical variables are demonstrated as numbers and percentages of the total, except for g- and ptc-based subgroups (listed below $AMR_{prob} > 0.2$), where the percentages refer to the total number of cases with $AMR_{prob} > 0.2$ in each column. Continuous variables are shown as median (IQR; Q1, Q3). As different training sets were used to establish molecular injury scores, semiquantitative categories are demonstrated (minimal, mild, moderate, extensive).

AKI, acute kidney injury; AMR, antibody-mediated rejection; aTCMR, acute T cell-mediated rejection; bTCMR, borderline T cell-mediated rejection; caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection; EABMR, early-stage AMR; FABMR, fully-developed AMR; g, glomerulitis; IFTA, interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; i-FTA, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; IQR, interquartile range; IRRAT, injury-related repair-associated transcripts; ISO-T, isolated tubulitis; LABMR, late-stage AMR; MMDx, Molecular Microscope Diagnostic System; NRI, no rejection or injury; ptc, peritubular capillaritis; TCMR, T cell-mediated rejection; $TCMR_{prob}$, probability of molecular acute TCMR; v, arteritis.

2.4. Ethical approval

All participants signed a general consent form. The responsible ethics commissions gave full approval for the investigation (BASEC 2020-02817 and A13-02-01), and the investigation complied with the Declaration of Helsinki.

2.5. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 29.0 and GraphPad Prism Version 10.4.1. Kruskal-Wallis or Mann-Whitney *U* tests were used to compare continuous variables. Correlations were assessed using Spearman's rank test. Binary logistic regression was applied to calculate odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for the association between histologic lesions and $TCMR_{prob}$. Univariable Cox regression was used to calculate hazard ratios (HRs) with 95% CI for associations between histologic or molecular variables and time to event. Given the low case and event number, only univariable testing was performed. Kaplan-Meier survival curves were compared using log-rank tests. For univariable Cox regression, correlation analyses, and binary logistic regression, variables with missing values were analyzed based on available data. Continuous data were reported as mean \pm standard deviation or median with interquartile range (Q1-Q3). Categorical data were presented as counts (n) and percentages (%). A 2-sided *P* value $< .05$ was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Baseline characteristics

Within the Banff-defined caTCMR ($n = 26$), the median (interquartile range) age at biopsy was 53 years (41-61), and 38% of patients were female. The median time of biopsy posttransplant in caTCMR biopsies was 13 months (4-53), whereas biopsies from the whole study cohort occurred earlier (median 6 months [2-53]). Of the caTCMR biopsies, 77% were indication biopsies. Baseline characteristics are summarized in [Table 1](#)¹⁶ and [Supplementary Table 2](#). [Table 2](#) illustrates histologic characteristics.

3.2. Molecular TCMR activity and signals among caTCMR

[Figure 2A](#) and [Table 3](#) demonstrate $TCMR_{prob}$ values across all histologic subgroups, with further molecular information provided in [Supplementary Table 3](#). Within caTCMR, cases with concomitant aTCMR had significantly higher median $TCMR_{prob}$ than “pure” caTCMR (0.54 [0.30-0.83] vs 0.03 [0.01-0.28]; $P = .012$) and caTCMR with bTCMR (0.54 [0.30-0.83] vs 0.01 [0.01-0.77]; $P = .036$). Their median $TCMR_{prob}$ was similar to aTCMR without caTCMR features in the positive control group ($P = .505$). Thirteen of 26 (50%) caTCMR cases had $TCMR_{prob} > 0.2$, most frequently in caTCMR with aTCMR (88%; [Fig. 2B](#)). Of these, 9 of 13 (69%) were classified as molecular TCMR and 4 of 13 (31%) as mixed molecular AMR/TCMR by molecular signals. Conversely, 14 of 40 (35%) cases in the positive control

Table 4

Subgroup with “pure” caTCMR in detail.

Case no.	Indication	t	ti	i-IFTA	t-IFTA	g	ptc	ci	ct	DSA	TCMR _{prob}	AMR _{prob}	IFTA score	ct >1 _{prob}	Archetype	Molecular sign-outs	Treatment
1	Protocol	2	2	2	3	1	0	2	2	No	0.05	0.15	0.86	0.77	R1 (NRI)	No molecular rejection	No specific treatment
2	eGFR, DSA	2	3	3	2	0	0	3	3	dnDSA	0.28	0.28	0.80	0.76	R2 (TCMR)	TCMR	Steroids
3	Proteinuria	2	3	3	NA	0	0	3	3	No	0.24	0.09	0.98	0.97	R2 (TCMR)	Possible TCMR	No specific treatment
4	eGFR, DSA	2	2	2	3	0	0	2	2	pDSA	0.32	0.41	0.94	0.94	R2 (TCMR)	TCMR	T cell depletion
5	eGFR	2	2	2	3	0	0	2	2	No	0.02	0.02	0.49	0.49	R1 (NRI)	No molecular rejection	No specific treatment
6	Protocol	2	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	No	0.01	0.13	0.25	0.25	R4 (EABMR)	AMR	Steroids
7	eGFR, DSA, proteinuria	1	2	3	2	0	0	2	2	dnDSA	0.01	0.02	0.61	0.57	R1 (NRI)	No molecular rejection	Intensification of maintenance IS
8	Protocol	1	2	2	3	0	0	2	2	No	0.30	0.06	0.37	0.37	R2 (TCMR)	TCMR	Steroids
9	Protocol	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	No	0.01	0.08	0.39	0.39	R1 (NRI)	No molecular rejection	No specific treatment
10	Proteinuria	0	2	2	2	0	1	2	2	No	0.01	0.06	0.63	0.60	R1 (NRI)	No molecular rejection	No specific treatment
11	eGFR	2	3	3	NA	0	0	3	3	No	0.03	0.19	0.62	0.52	R1 (NRI)	Rejection, no AMR/TCMR	Steroids

Clinical, histologic (Banff lesions), serologic (DSA presence), and molecular details (classifier scores, molecular archetype, and molecular sign-outs) are listed for each case. All cases have no interstitial inflammation (i0) and no concomitant borderline TCMR/acute TCMR. Case 11 represents 1 case of “pure” caTCMR stage II (with v2). IFTA scores are demonstrated as continuous variables regardless of the possibility of different training sets. Boldface values signify TCMR_{prob} or AMR_{prob} above the upper limit of normal.

AMR, antibody-mediated rejection; caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection; ci, interstitial fibrosis; ct, tubular atrophy; dnDSA, de novo donor-specific antibody; DSA, donor-specific antibody; EABMR, early-stage AMR; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; g, glomerulitis; IFTA, interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; i-IFTA, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; IS, immunosuppression; NA, not available; NRI, no rejection or injury; pDSA, preformed donor-specific antibody; ptc, peritubular capillaritis; t, tubulitis; TCMR, T cell-mediated rejection; TCMR_{prob}, probability of molecular acute TCMR; ti, total inflammation; t-IFTA, tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy.

A

TCMR continuum (n=66)

B

Inflammation spectrum (n=243)

A + B + C

(caption on next page)

group exceeded $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$, with the highest rate in aTCMR grade IA/IB (88%). Subthreshold and negative controls showed significantly lower median $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ and fewer cases with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$, particularly in “i-IFTA ≥ 2 alone” and isolated tubulitis (ISO-T) subgroups (no cases > 0.2). Within the 11 “pure” caTCMR cases, 4 of 11 (36%) biopsies had $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$ and belonged to R2 (TCMR) archetype clusters (Table 4). All 4 of these cases were called molecular TCMR (one possible TCMR) by molecular sign-outs. Additionally, 2 of 4 (50%) had $\text{AMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$. When compared to the 7 cases with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} < 0.2$, histologic lesions did not differ relevantly.

3.3. Correlations and associations between histologic Banff lesions and molecular scores within the TCMR continuum and inflammation spectrum

To explore the relationship between histologic Banff lesions and TCMR-specific molecular scores, we performed a correlation analysis across the TCMR continuum ($n = 66$), displayed in Figure 3A with additional information in Supplementary Table 4. Banff i-, t-, and ti-lesions correlated mildly with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ ($r = 0.51$, 0.52 , and $r = 0.33$, respectively; all $P < .01$). Conversely, neither i-IFTA nor t-IFTA-lesions correlated with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ ($r = 0.04$ and 0.06 ; both $P > .05$) but instead correlated better with $\text{ct} > 1_{\text{prob}}$. In univariable logistic regression models (model 1, Table 5), i-, t-, peritubular capillaritis (ptc)-, and ti-lesions were each significantly associated with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$, with the strongest univariable association for i-, t-, and ti-lesions (all $P < .01$). To explore how increasing Banff lesion severity relates to molecular TCMR activity across the inflammation spectrum, we extended the analysis to 243 biopsies, comprising all cases from the TCMR continuum and subthreshold controls (Fig. 3B). Median $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ increased significantly with higher i-, t-, v-, and ti-lesions (all $P < .001$), but not i-IFTA ($P = .155$). $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ increased modestly with higher t-IFTA ($P = .017$); however, also cases with t-IFTA3 demonstrated median $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ below 0.2. Higher i-IFTA and t-IFTA scores were significantly associated with increased tubular atrophy (ct) $> 1_{\text{prob}}$ and molecular IFTA scores (Supplementary Fig. S2). Within the inflammation spectrum ($n = 243$), $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ distributions differed by both IFTA severity and the location of inflammation (Supplementary Fig. S3). In cases without or with mild IFTA (interstitial fibrosis [ci] + $\text{ct} \leq 2$), higher $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ values were mainly correlating with elevated i-lesions (mirrored by higher ti). In contrast, in moderate and severe IFTA ($\text{ci} + \text{ct} > 2$), some biopsies with $i < 2$ but i-IFTA ≥ 2 displayed elevated $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ (also mirrored by higher ti).

Histologic and molecular cutoffs were compared across cohorts (Supplementary Tables 5 and 6). Sixty-eight percent of

histologic $t \geq 2$ within caTCMR corresponded to molecular $t > 1_{\text{prob}} > 0.1$. Furthermore, 100% of $i \geq 2$ in caTCMR matched $i > 1_{\text{prob}} > 0.06$. In contrast, $\text{ct} \geq 2$ and $\text{ci} \geq 2$ showed weaker alignment (low sensitivity of 0.11–0.17) with histology as reference. With molecular lesions as reference, the sensitivity of the IFTA score > 0.83 to predict histologic scores $\text{ci}/\text{ct} \geq 2$ and IFTA ≥ 4 increased (0.75–1), but with low PPV/specificity (0.07–0.16 and 0.05–0.25 for $\text{ci}/\text{ct} \geq 2$, respectively).

3.4. Molecular AMR activity, mixed signals, and injury scores

Molecular AMR_{prob} across subgroups is presented in Table 3 and Supplementary Figure S4. Among caTCMR cases, 7 of 26 (27%) had $\text{AMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$, most frequent in caTCMR with concomitant aTCMR (38%). Among these cases, 5 of 7 (71%) had donor-specific antibodies at the time of biopsy, 4 of 7 (57%) showed histologic signs of glomerulitis (g)- or ptc-lesions, while 3 of 7 (43%) had g0 ptc0 . Of positive controls, 35% had $\text{AMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$, most pronounced in aTCMR (with 5 of 5 having g0 ptc0 by histology). Among subthreshold and negative controls, few cases had elevated AMR_{prob} . Of note, in total, 27 of 48 (56%) cases with $\text{AMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$ among the total study cohort ($n = 374$) did not have signs of MVI (g0 ptc0 ; Table 3). The distribution of $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ and AMR_{prob} across all main subgroups is illustrated in Figure 4. The highest rate of biopsies with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ and AMR_{prob} above the upper limit of normal (mixed molecular phenotypes) was observed among caTCMR, with 7 of 26 (27%), followed by the positive control with 7 of 40 (18%). Only 5 of these 14 cases had MVI (1 case with g1 ptc0 and 4 cases with g0 ptc1 ; all Fig. 4).

Regarding injury scores, higher histologic i-, t-, and v-lesions were progressively associated with AKI (IRRAT) scores, while i-IFTA- and t-IFTA-lesions correlated with IFTA scores (Supplementary Fig. S2). Higher AKI scores were more common in aTCMR-related subgroups, whereas higher IFTA scores were observed primarily in caTCMR cases (Table 2).

3.5. Overlapping pathologies with formally fulfilled caTCMR criteria

Thirty-three biopsies with superimposed pathologies, including AMR/MVI, mixed rejection, BKN, GN, or pyelonephritis, formally fulfilled histologic caTCMR lesion criteria. Molecular TCMR activity varied by underlying condition, with higher $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ in BKN (0.65 [0.20–0.91]) and pyelonephritis (0.19 [0.08–0.28]), compared to AMR or GN, which displayed higher AMR_{prob} (Supplementary Table 7 and Supplementary Fig. S5).

Figure 3. Correlation of histologic Banff lesions with molecular scores. (A) Correlation matrix of all 66 cases within the T cell-mediated rejection (TCMR) continuum demonstrating the correlations of key histologic and molecular parameters compared by Spearman’s rank test. Histologic Banff lesions relevant for chronic-active TCMR and their correlations with the probability of molecular acute TCMR ($\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$) are highlighted (arrow). For tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy (t-IFTA), data on $n = 53$ are available. (B) Relationship between semiquantitative histologic TCMR-related Banff lesions (interstitial inflammation [i]-, tubulitis [t]-, arteritis [v]-, total inflammation [ti]-, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy [i-IFTA]-, and t-IFTA-lesions) and $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ in 243 cases within the inflammation spectrum. For t-IFTA, data on $n = 211$ are available. The results are demonstrated as median (interquartile range), as well as individual biopsy cases (dots). The Kruskal-Wallis test was applied to compare groups. ci, interstitial fibrosis; ct, tubular atrophy; g, glomerulitis; ptc, peritubular capillaritis.

Table 5
Histologic predictors of $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$.

Variable	β (estimate)	OR	95% CI (low-high)	P
i-lesion	1.230	3.420	1.689-8.232	.002
t-lesion	1.482	4.400	2.063-10.88	.0004
v-lesion	0.838	2.313	0.993-5.907	.061
g-lesion	0.304	1.355	0.509-3.687	.534
ptc-lesion	0.979	2.663	1.147-7.571	.035
ti-lesion	1.037	2.821	1.502-5.861	.0025
i-IFTA-lesion	0.185	1.204	0.803-1.821	.371
t-IFTA-lesion ^a	0.310	1.364	0.833-2.270	.220
Indication eGFR	0.916	2.500	0.906-7.337	.084
Indication proteinuria	-1.089	0.337	0.017-2.442	.343
Indication dnDSA	0.420	1.522	0.330-7.029	.579
Protocol biopsy	-1.012	0.363	0.104-1.112	.077

Univariable binary logistic regression model for histologic predictors of $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$ among $n = 66$ cases within the TCMR continuum (Banff-defined chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection, $n = 26$, and positive control, $n = 0$).

CI, confidence interval; dnDSA, de novo donor-specific antibody; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; g, glomerulitis; i, interstitial inflammation; i-IFTA, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; OR, odds ratio; ptc, peritubular capillaritis; t, tubulitis; TCMR, T cell-mediated rejection; $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$, probability of molecular acute TCMR; ti, total inflammation; t-IFTA, tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; v, arteritis.

^a Data on $n = 53$.

By molecular sign-outs, 87% of BKN cases and 64% of pyelonephritis were called molecular TCMR (possible/full) or AMR/TCMR.

3.6. Associations of $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ and other parameters with allograft outcomes

The association of $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ with allograft outcomes was assessed using Cox regression models (Table 6). In the whole study cohort, $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$ was associated with a higher risk of the composite renal endpoint (HR 3.744, 95% CI 1.663-8.429, $P = .001$) and allograft loss (HR 6.876, 95% CI 2.242-21.088, $P < .001$), alongside AMR_{prob}, AKI, and IFTA scores (all significant in univariable testing). Histologically, higher IFTA and relevant glomerulosclerosis ($> 20\%$) were associated with higher risk, while higher i-lesions were associated with allograft loss (model 2: HR 2.164, 95% CI 1.303-3.596, $P = .003$). Of note, proteinuria as a biopsy indication was associated with allograft failure. Among the TCMR continuum, only higher $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ was associated with higher risk for the composite renal endpoint or allograft loss ($P = .016$ and $.004$, respectively; Supplementary Table 8). Kaplan-Meier survival curves showed higher allograft loss with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}} > 0.2$ in the overall cohort and TCMR continuum (log-rank test, $P < .05$; Fig. 5A, B), with a nonsignificant trend in caTCMR ($P = .120$; Fig. 5C). Among histologic subgroups, caTCMR cases and the positive control had higher rates of graft failure within 36 months, than subthreshold and negative

controls (Fig. 6A). Furthermore, conventional TCMR treatment in caTCMR cases ($n = 14$) was not associated with better outcomes; notably, all 3 allograft failures occurred in treated patients (Supplementary Fig. S6). Comparing histologic and molecular cutoffs demonstrated that molecular IFTA scores > 0.83 , $i > 1_{\text{prob}} > 0.06$, and $t > 1_{\text{prob}} > 0.1$ provided clearer separation of graft survival curves than their histologic counterparts, with wider divergence between subgroups (Fig. 6B). Stratification based on cv-lesions did not demonstrate any difference (Fig. 6C). The median follow-up time was 19 months (10-29) in the whole cohort, 19 months (10-27) in the TCMR continuum, and 19 months (10-29) in caTCMR.

4. Discussion

This retrospective two-center observational study investigated the molecular profiles of caTCMR within the TCMR continuum and inflammation spectrum using MMDx, recognizing that it has not been trained on caTCMR.

Histologically, we observed that “pure” caTCMR without bTCMR/aTCMR is rare. In our total cohort of 755 biopsies, only 11 (1.5%) cases fulfilled these criteria, while 59 (7.8%) formally fulfilled criteria for caTCMR, regardless of concomitant bTCMR/aTCMR ($n = 15$) or overlapping pathologies ($n = 33$). This variation in frequencies, depending on how strictly the Banff criteria are applied, mirrors previously reported ranges and potentially reflects the heterogeneity of caTCMR.¹⁻³ Before further investigations, we excluded cases with AMR/MVI, mixed rejection, and overlapping inflammatory pathologies, as these interfere with rejection classifiers or signify exclusion criteria for diagnosing caTCMR.^{5,17,18}

The highest $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ values within Banff-defined caTCMR were observed in caTCMR cases with aTCMR, comparable to aTCMR without caTCMR from the positive control cohort. Literature demonstrated that $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$ correlates most with high $i + t$ scores, indicating its training on aTCMR ($i > 1$ and $t > 1$).^{14,19} Also in our investigation, Banff i-, t- and ti-lesions showed the best correlation with $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$. In contrast, “pure” caTCMR (i0) and subthreshold cases exhibited lower $\text{TCMR}_{\text{prob}}$, whereas isolated lesions as ISO-T and “i-IFTA ≥ 2 alone,” were associated with only minimal rejection activity. These findings align with prior reports implying that isolated lesions (like ISO-T) are benign, also from a molecular perspective.^{14,20,21}

Most Banff lesions within caTCMR have been studied individually, with varying findings. Although isolated tubulitis is considered benign, studies on the association between i-IFTA and graft failure yielded heterogeneous results. Although some investigations linked i-IFTA, either as a late marker of under-immunosuppression or residual inflammation after aTCMR, to long-term graft failure, findings from the DeKAF cohort did not confirm a clear connection between i-IFTA scores and allograft loss.^{1,22-25} Previous molecular studies linked inflammation in scarred areas to mast cell transcripts (eg, carboxypeptidase A3, CPA3), which are associated with adverse outcomes and, as demonstrated by Kung et al,¹⁰ may indicate treatment resistance in caTCMR.⁷ Notably, within the MMDx classifiers, CPA3 is included among mast cell-related transcripts captured by the IFTA score, which in our study cohort was associated with graft

Figure 4. Molecular acute T cell-mediated rejection (TCMR) and antibody-mediated rejection (AMR) activity within the main subgroups. The scatter plot with AMR_{prob} (y-axis) and probability of molecular acute TCMR (TCMR_{prob}) (x-axis) is demonstrated for all 374 biopsies, categorized based on the main subgroups. The dotted lines indicate the thresholds for the upper limit of normal (ULN) of molecular acute TCMR or AMR. Percentages of cases above both ULN thresholds are listed for all subgroups. Additionally, for cases above both ULN thresholds (n = 16) and cases with AMR_{prob} <0.2 but TCMR_{prob} >0.2 (n = 17), the histologic microvascular inflammation (MVI) score is marked next to the corresponding dot as either “0” (meaning both glomerulitis [g]0 and peritubular capillaritis [ptc]0), g1 (meaning g1 ptc0) or ptc1 (meaning g0 ptc1). caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection.

failure.^{6,26} In our examination, higher i-IFTA was not associated with TCMR_{prob} or adverse outcomes directly, but correlated with molecular chronicity markers (ct>1_{prob} and IFTA scores). Thus, i-IFTA may persist as a residual lesion after active inflammation and appears to align more with molecular chronicity than with TCMR activity.^{24,25} Its correlation with the molecular IFTA score in our cohort may partly explain why treated caTCMR cases failed to respond to conventional TCMR therapy, though this observation should be interpreted cautiously, given the limited strength of the analysis. Likewise, t-IFTA was mainly linked to chronic molecular injury.

Total inflammation (ti), however, was associated with molecular TCMR activity (TCMR_{prob} >0.2) in our analysis within the TCMR continuum. Although ti reflects the combined effects of i and i-IFTA, this association highlights the value in representing overall active inflammation. An earlier study demonstrated that ti outperforms i in predicting molecular disturbance in allografts, particularly cytotoxic T cell burden relevant to TCMR transcripts.²⁷ In our cohort, this may suggest that under advanced IFTA, high i-IFTA can also contribute to a molecular TCMR signal, mirrored by ti, even when i is low or absent (Supplementary Fig. S3).

Interestingly, 27% of caTCMR biopsies showed mixed molecular rejection features, sometimes even with g0 ptc0. Prior observations by Halloran et al²⁸ reported an association of i-IFTA with molecular AMR. However, among their cohort, a substantial number of molecular AMR cases showed histologic AMR features. In contrast, we excluded biopsies with histologic

AMR/MVI, and we observed no significant association between i-IFTA and AMR_{prob}. We hypothesize that mixed molecular phenotypes may arise from other caTCMR lesions, chronic lesions, or a combination of subtle histologic and serologic indicators of AMR. Conversely, our previous study, with fewer histologic rejection cases (especially caTCMR) and a focus on molecular sign-outs, reported a low rate of molecular AMR in MVI-absent cases.²⁹ However, a small fraction yielded molecular AMR signals, at least with subthreshold findings. Whether such cases (here with additional AMR_{prob} >0.2) benefit from dual or tailored treatment approaches needs further investigation, as MMDx, particularly in histologically discrepant cases, could help guide therapeutic decisions.³⁰

From a molecular sign-out perspective, caTCMR cases displayed heterogeneous profiles. Of 26 biopsies, 9 were classified as molecular TCMR (8 predominant R2 archetypes), 4 as mixed rejection (1 R2 archetype and 3 R3 archetypes), and 2 as molecular AMR, while 11 were classified as no rejection (R1). The predominance of R2 archetypes suggests that caTCMR in our study primarily reflected a TCMR-like molecular pattern, characterized by tubulitis, molecular injury, and atrophy-fibrosis.³¹ However, different molecular rejection profiles emerged. These insights may help distinguish patients benefiting from targeted anti-TCMR or combination therapies, although R1 and IFTA-associated profiles may argue against intensive treatment and support optimization of maintenance immunosuppression and nephroprotective care. We have previously shown that

Table 6
Impact of histologic and molecular parameters on composite renal endpoint or allograft loss.

Variables	Model 1: composite renal endpoint (n = 327)				Model 2: allograft loss (n = 327)			
	β (estimate)	HR	95% CI (low-high)	P	β (estimate)	HR	95% CI (low-high)	P
Molecular parameters								
TCMR _{prob}	2.346	10.444	3.272-33.336	<.001	3.661	38.903	9.098-166.354	<.001
AMR _{prob}	4.237	69.169	9.325-513.079	<.001	3.613	37.075	1.906-721.283	.017
TCMR _{prob} >0.2 (yes)	1.320	3.744	1.663-8.429	.001	1.928	6.876	2.242-21.088	<.001
AMR _{prob} >0.2 (yes)	1.444	4.240	1.933-9.299	<.001	1.371	3.938	1.206-12.861	.023
AKI score moderate/extensive (yes)	0.896	2.450	1.188-5.049	.015	1.566	4.788	1.564-14.654	.006
IFTA score moderate/extensive (yes)	0.823	2.277	1.110-4.673	.025	0.867	2.379	0.799-7.086	.119
i >1 _{prob} >0.06 (yes)	1.173	3.231	1.576-6.624	.001	1.429	4.176	1.401-12.447	.010
t >1 _{prob} >0.1 (yes)	1.198	3.313	1.608-6.824	.001	1.287	3.620	1.215-10.785	.021
IFTA score >0.83 (yes)	1.289	3.629	1.477-8.919	.005	1.959	7.091	2.171-23.155	.001
ct >1 _{prob} >0.84 (yes)	1.251	3.493	1.331-9.170	.011	1.770	5.873	1.606-21.474	.007
Histologic parameters								
i-lesion	0.337	1.401	0.909-2.160	.127	0.772	2.164	1.303-3.596	.003
t-lesion	0.124	1.132	0.749-1.709	.556	0.501	1.650	0.940-2.895	.081
ti-lesion	0.225	1.253	0.855-1.834	.247	0.422	1.525	0.896-2.597	.120
i-IFTA-lesion	0.128	1.137	0.839-1.539	.408	0.224	1.251	0.794-1.970	.335
t-IFTA-lesion ^a	0.247	1.280	0.796-2.057	.309	0.509	1.663	0.824-3.356	.156
ci + ct-lesion	0.307	1.359	1.099-1.681	.005	0.309	1.361	0.974-1.903	.071
ah-lesion	0.445	1.560	1.049-2.322	.028	0.206	1.229	0.670-2.255	.505
i ≥2 (yes)	0.236	1.266	0.301-5.331	.748	1.256	3.512	0.771-15.992	.104
t ≥2 (yes)	0.344	1.410	0.604-3.296	.427	1.150	3.158	1.030-9.687	.044
ti ≥2 (yes)	0.428	1.534	0.587-4.009	.382	0.811	2.250	0.619-8.181	.218
i-IFTA ≥2 (yes)	0.298	1.347	0.640-2.835	.433	0.438	1.549	0.505-4.748	.444
t-IFTA ≥2 (yes) ^a	0.489	1.631	0.561-4.743	.369	1.007	2.736	0.552-13.567	.218
ci ≥2 (yes)	1.087	2.966	1.406-6.256	.004	1.120	3.064	0.993-9.453	.051
ct ≥2 (yes)	1.085	2.960	1.403-6.244	.004	1.118	3.057	0.991-9.434	.052
ci + ct ≥4 (yes)	1.097	2.994	1.420-6.315	.004	1.134	3.109	1.008-9.591	.048
cv >2 (yes)	0.490	1.632	0.696-3.830	.260	0.455	1.576	0.428-5.796	.494
ah + aah ≥2 (yes)	0.473	1.605	0.748-3.443	.225	0.164	1.178	0.383-3.624	.775
>20% glomerulosclerosis (yes) ^b	0.874	2.397	1.162-4.945	.018	1.392	4.022	1.350-11.979	.012
Biopsy indication								
Indication eGFR (yes)	0.173	1.189	0.580-2.436	.637	1.232	3.429	0.943-12.466	.061
Indication proteinuria (yes)	0.833	2.301	1.087-4.870	.029	1.376	3.957	1.321-11.858	.014
Indication dnDSA (yes)	-0.478	0.620	0.253-1.521	.296	-0.686	0.504	0.112-2.274	.372
Protocol biopsy (yes)	-0.030	0.971	0.369-2.554	.952	No events			

Univariable Cox regression models investigating the influence of different parameters on the composite renal endpoint (model 1: persistent eGFR decline >30%, persistent eGFR below 15 mL/min/1.73 m² or return to dialysis) and allograft loss (model 2: persistent eGFR below 15 mL/min/1.73 m² or return to dialysis) in the study cohort (n = 327 after exclusion of 6 biopsies with primary nonfunction and 41 repeated biopsies). Cox regression models restricted to the TCMR continuum are demonstrated in the [Supplementary Table 8](#).

aah, hyaline arteriolar thickening; ah, arteriolar hyalinosis; AKI, acute kidney injury; AMR, antibody-mediated rejection; CI, confidence interval; ci, interstitial fibrosis; ct, tubular atrophy; cv, vascular fibrous intimal thickening; dnDSA, de novo donor-specific antibody; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; HR, hazard ratio; i, interstitial inflammation; IFTA, interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; i-IFTA, interstitial inflammation in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy; t, tubulitis; TCMR, T cell-mediated rejection; TCMR_{prob}, probability of molecular acute TCMR; ti, total inflammation; t-IFTA, tubulitis in areas of interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy.

^a Data on n = 287.

^b Data on n = 322.

Figure 5. Allograft survival based on molecular acute T cell-mediated rejection (TCMR) classifier activity. Kaplan-Meier survival curves comparing subgroups stratified by probability of molecular acute TCMR (TCMR_{prob}) >0.2 (red) and <0.2 (green) with respect to a composite renal endpoint (left) or allograft loss (right). Groups were compared using the log-rank test. Censored individuals are demonstrated as black serrates. (A) Study cohort of n = 327 (6 cases with primary nonfunction excluded, as well as 41 repeated biopsies) stratified by TCMR_{prob}; (B) TCMR continuum (n = 63, 3 cases with primary nonfunction excluded) stratified by TCMR_{prob}; (C) Banff-defined chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection (caTCMR) (n = 23, 3 cases with primary nonfunction excluded).

Figure 6. Allograft survival based on histologic subgroups and molecular scores. Kaplan-Meier survival curves comparing subgroups within the study cohort ($n = 327$) stratified by different aspects with respect to a composite renal endpoint. Groups were compared using the log-rank test; in (B), $n = 327$ were either compared based on histologic stratification or molecular stratification. Censored individuals are demonstrated as black serrates. (A) Main histologic subgroups within the study cohort; (B) stratification by histologic interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy (IFTA) or corresponding molecular IFTA score cutoffs (top), histologic interstitial inflammation (i)-lesions or corresponding molecular $i > 1_{\text{prob}}$ cutoffs (middle), and histologic tubulitis (t)-lesions or corresponding molecular $t > 1_{\text{prob}}$ cutoffs (bottom); (C) Stratification based on vascular fibrous intimal thickening (cv)-lesions. caTCMR, chronic-active T cell-mediated rejection; ci, interstitial fibrosis; ct, tubular atrophy.

MMDx classifiers are responsive to antirejection therapies in follow-up biopsies.³² Nonetheless, only prospective interventional studies could conclude the relevance of molecular profiling in caTCMR.

In our observation, higher AKI (IRRAT) scores were linked to active lesions ($i + t$, especially in aTCMR), whereas higher IFTA scores predominated in caTCMR and chronic subthreshold controls. Both were associated with outcomes and, alongside rejection classifiers, may additionally help distinguish scenarios where intensified antirejection therapy is appropriate (eg, high AKI, low IFTA) vs those better managed with

conventional nephroprotection (high IFTA). Previous studies in AMR already highlighted the independent prognostic value of injury scores.³³

In superimposed pathologies, the molecular profile mirrored the dominant lesion. For example, a relevant proportion of cases with BKN (with formally fulfilled caTCMR criteria) exhibited similar molecular TCMR signals as aTCMR, while also 64% of pyelonephritis cases showed TCMR_{prob} of at least >0.1 . Cases with GN more often demonstrated molecular AMR activity. These findings illustrate a key limitation: MMDx cannot reliably distinguish the origin of tubulointerstitial inflammation, which

may reflect alloimmune injury (TCMR) or infection, particularly BKN/pyelonephritis. It was previously shown that additional diagnoses can mimic molecular rejection signals and that developing a “BKN-specific” classifier remains challenging.^{18,34} These findings emphasize that MMDx results must always be interpreted within the clinical context. TCMR_{prob} elevations in patients without virological evidence of BKN or other infections most likely reflect alloimmunity, whereas in the presence of infection, they may represent virus-driven inflammation. Hence, MMDx cannot serve as a stand-alone biomarker to guide therapy. Earlier histologic studies have also shown that in cases with elevated i-IFTA, the underlying progressive pathology (like BKN or GN) drives outcomes apart from inflammation itself.³⁵

In our cohort, several molecular rejection classifiers and injury scores were associated with graft failure, while histologic predictors were mainly markers of chronicity, such as higher IFTA or glomerulosclerosis. Within the TCMR continuum, only TCMR_{prob} (continuous) showed a slight association with graft failure. All these findings should be interpreted cautiously, given the limited follow-up and low number of events. Kaplan-Meier analyses suggested somewhat clearer outcome separation with molecular $i > 1_{\text{prob}}$, $t > 1_{\text{prob}}$, and IFTA compared to histologic counterparts, possibly reflecting an advantage of continuous molecular assessment over semiquantitative histologic scoring. These observations are descriptive rather than ultimate, and prospective studies will be needed to directly compare MMDx with histology in outcome prediction.

This study has several limitations. First, the number of caTCMR cases was limited, reflecting its rarity, and MMDx was never trained on caTCMR. Second, the observational design limits causal inference, particularly regarding treatment response and outcomes. Third, although MMDx provides molecular insights, it samples a limited biopsy portion and may not capture focal pathology, possibly reflected by only moderate correlations in our study. Presumably, only spatial transcriptomics could address this issue. Additionally, excluding cases with overlapping pathologies or AMR/MVI to isolate the TCMR spectrum may have reduced generalizability, along with the lack of an external validation cohort. Finally, although we included outcomes, the follow-up time and treatment information were not standardized, and interventional studies are needed to close this gap.

In conclusion, within our retrospective two-center observational study with a small sample of 26 caTCMR cases, MMDx identified relevant molecular TCMR activity in a subset, primarily with higher degrees of i , t , and ti . In advanced IFTA stages with absent active i , ti likely reflected higher i-IFTA and may have been associated with molecular TCMR signals, consistent with i-IFTA persisting as residual inflammation in scarred areas. Some caTCMR cases also showed molecular AMR activity, underscoring overlap within this phenotype. Whether molecular diagnostics can meaningfully complement histology in guiding diagnosis and treatment decisions for caTCMR will require larger, external validation and prospective interventional studies.

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Author contributions

L.W. and T.S. designed and directed the project and performed the analysis. L.W. wrote the manuscript. P.H., E.G., D.H., K.J., K.H., E.R., K.C.L., A.G., B.M.H., F.W., B.G., S.v.M., L.V., and O.V. assisted with data collection and the review of the manuscript.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors of this manuscript have no conflicts of interest to disclose as described by *American Journal of Transplantation*.

Data availability

The data supporting this study's findings are available on request from the corresponding author, Lukas Weidmann. However, the data are not publicly available due to restrictions, such as the fact that they contain information that could compromise the privacy of research participants.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajt.2025.12.288>.

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